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THE COMEBACK OF BATA : (CASE STUDY)

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ABSTRACT

Indian footwear industry is second largest next to China and it is segmented in two ways namely organised sector and unorganised sector. Organised sector includes market players like Bata, Liberty, Adidas, Metro etc and it serves to 1/3rd of the market. The unorganized sector serves the rest 2/3rd. Further it is more segmented into men, women and kids market. Mostly women and kids are catered by the unorganized sector.

Bata, it may not be exaggerated, if I say, that there would be no one in India who would not know this name. Most of us are brought up wearing those shoes, chappals with white sole and blue straps. The unanimous name known for footwear was Bata in 1980s. Families used to visit these showrooms for their entire family purchase, be it for children, women, men, formal or informals or executive one stop for all. It may not be exaggerated if I say that the company enjoyed almost monopoly those years. Later on, Bata started outsourcing for their products and the quality gradually eroded away along with the brand name. Many people who were real loyalists for the company also shifted to other brands.

The company realised it very late and started reengineering their product line and their strategies. Meanwhile many other companies took part of its market share leaving a little for Bata. The company suffered at its top as well as bottom level making huge ultimate losses finally in early 2000s. Soon, the company started reworking, but this would take time to change the perception of the people.

This case study highlights the various strategies adopted by the Bata Management in the current market trends with increased competition from local players and Chinese imports. Bata usually targets lower middle and middle class segments of the society, but now it is contemplating changes to survive in the competition. This paper deals all these issues in detail and offers few suggestions as well for its future recourse.

Keywords: Bata, Chinese imports, reinvention, future strategies, SWOT analysis, BCG Matrix, Product Development, Research.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Bata is the favourite footwear brand in India. It is the largest retailer and leading manufacturer of footwear in India. The company was actually born as T&A Bata Co. in 1894 in Zlin, Czechoslovakia (Czech Republic) and it entered India in 1931. The company is incorporated as Bata Shoe Company Private Limited, set up as a small operation in Konnagar (near Calcutta) in 1932. By 1934, the foundation stone was laid for the first building of Bata's operation. The overall site was doubled in area in the following years. This town ship is called Batanagar and it was also the first manufacturing facility in the Indian shoe industry to receive the ISO: 9001 certification.

The company changed its name as Bata India Limited after going public in 1973. Today, Bata India is the largest footwear retailer in India. Its extensive network of over 1200 stores across India is unmatched to its competitors. Their stores are present in good locations in all the cities and towns. The Bata store is one of the most recognizable and favored landmarks in major cities in India. Their stores offer a superior shopping experience to the customers with better quality products. In addition to the retail stores, Bata operates non-retail distribution network through its urban wholesale division in large scale catering to the millions of customers through over 30,000 dealers.

1.1 Indian footwear Industry

Indian footwear market is estimated at about Rs. 19,900 crore with a growth rate of 8 –10 percent (according to the data provided by market advisors in September 2011). The category covers casual, formal, semi formal and sports shoes along with sandals for men and women. Men’s segment accounts for 59 percent and women’s at 41 percent. Casual footwear dominates nearly two-third of the total footwear market. Out of these again exclusive brand outlets account for 50 percent and by multi brand outlets at 28 percent. The preference to the branded products is increasing as the consumers are willing to buy from malls and other organized retail stores.

Figure-1: Share of Leather & Non- Leather Footwear Footwear Production (2012-13)

Indian footwear industry was dominated by the unorganised sector with a share of 70% in 2012. The unorganized segment comprises of small cottage industry based manufacturers. The organized sector comprising of major domestic and international players like Bata, Liberty, Adidas and Metro etc, accounted for only 30% of the market. The organized sector continues to grow rapidly as the customers are willing to pay extra for the quality. Their changing life styles and larger portion of disposable income is also a factor for this. The present size of the market is Rs. 13,750 crores out of which organized sector is 37 percent. It is the second largest after China.

The organized segment can incorporate advanced technologies in production to increase their market share which is not possible for the unorganized sector. Adidas has launched a new shoe with superior cushion, optimal fit and temperature independence. With such advancements, the organized sector is expected to develop at a high rate than the current rate of 10 – 15 %.

Figure-2: Share of Organized and Unorganized Sector in Footwear Market (2012)

Source: ASSOCHAM

1.2 Market Segmentation

The footwear market can be segmented into men, women and kids market and their share in 2012 is shown in the following figure.

S. No	Market Segment	Market share
1	Men	55%
2	Women	30%
3	Kids	15%

Footwear market type in percentages in 2012

Source: RNCOS Estimation

Figure-5: Indian Footwear Market by Category (%) (2012)

Source: RNCOS Estimation

Further the footwear industry is again classified into casual footwear, mass footwear, premium and sports footwear. The mass footwear usually refers to low price footwear especially the slippers. The casual footwear is for daily wear for schools, colleges and workplaces etc. Usually the casual footwear dominates the mass footwear.

1.3 MARKET SIZE OF FOOT WEAR INDUSTRY IN INDIA

The share of the casual footwear is 61% in 2012 and is expected to dominate in the near future whereas the share of sports and premium segment is also expected to grow. The estimated size of the market is 16000 crores

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out of which 70 percent is unorganized. Indian footwear industry is 15 percent of global share. Many reputed brands like Nike, Reebok are already manufacturing in India and many more are trying to enter to retail in India.

Apart from serving local market, India also exports to other countries. This included both leather and non leather footwear in both men and women segments. India is a sleeping giant with an installed capacity of 1,800 million pairs only second to China. It has over 100 fully mechanized, modern shoe making plants with global standards. It also manufactures for some good brands like Florsheim (US), Lloyd (Germany), Clarks (UK), Marks and Spencer (UK). The main export markets for India are UK and USA both account for 55% of total exports. India has its major production centres at Chennai, Ranipet, Ambur in Tamil Nadu, Agra and Delhi. India offers benefits to other countries like low cost of production, abundant raw material, and has huge consumption market. Nearly 75% of the total exports come from Southern Region and Northern Region, with a share of 13%. Nearly 83% of market is from U.K., Germany, Italy, the USA, France, and Portugal. India is often referred to as the sleeping giant in footwear terms. It has an installed capacity of 1,800 million pairs, second only to China. But ladies segment was untapped and 80 – 90 percent of sales happen from unorganised market.

Figure Market Share (%) of Footwear Companies

India is on the threshold of the retail revolution and numerous international players are entering and will enter in near future too.

2.1 CURRENT TRENDS OF FOOTWEAR INDUSTRY

The Indian economy has shown a positive growth with gross domestic product expected to grow at a rate of 9 percent in 2011 – 12. The leather and footwear industry has been growing at 20 percent in 2008 – 2011. Footwear industry alone is 60 percent of the total exports in 2014 – 15. This clearly shows that the Indian economy is growing to become a footwear manufacturing centre across the globe.

2.2 The future of the footwear industry

The future of Indian footwear industry is very bright with the growing fashion consciousness, increased disposable income and abundance of raw materials.

The Indian footwear industry is anticipated to grow at a CAGR of around 9 percent during 2011 – 14. The estimated annual production capacity of leather shoe uppers is 112 million pairs during this period. Footwear market is Rs. 13,750 Crore and constitutes just about one percent of Indian retail. It is estimated to grow to Rs 22,000 crore to touch Rs.38,700 crore by 2015. It is growing at a CAGR of more than 20 percent. In future it is expected to grow at 25 percent. By 2025 it is expected to reach Rs. 47, 000 crores.

In 2010, the Indian footwear market is expected to have value of \$4,380.3 million, an increase of 62.1% since 2005.

India Footwear Market Value Forecast; \$ million, 2005-10

year	\$ million	INR billion	growth
2005	2701.5	119.2	9.10%
2006	2960.4	130.6	9.60%
2007	3256	143.6	10%
2008	3589.7	158.4	10.2%
2009	3963.8	174.9	10.4%
2010	4380.3	193.2	10.5%
2011		137.5	9 %
2012		220.0	15%
2015		387.0	20%
2025		470.0	25%

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Exports are also expected to grow at a CAGR of 15 percent in the next five years according to Assocham. The industry will focus on Europe and US.

The total footwear imports of US in 2012 were 2,28,19,69,730 pairs and out of which majority were from China. The share of India was just 0.6%.

3.1 ABOUT BATA

The company was founded in 1849 by Thomas Bata. Under Jan Antonín Bata the company grew quickly throughout Europe, North America, Asia and North Africa.

In 1931, Bata was started in India and traded on Kolkata and Mumbai Stock Exchanges. Bata Shoes is a large family owned Shoe Company based in Bermuda but, the current head quarters of Bata are in Lausanne, Switzerland. It has its retail presence in 50 countries and production facilities in 26 countries. The company operates three business units

- Bata metro markets
- Bata emerging markets
- Bata branded business

4.1 The 4 P's

PRODUCT: the products include all varieties such as shoes, canvas, rubber, leather shoes, sandals, school shoes, flip-flops etc.

PRICE: The price of the products is more consumer friendly and mostly are targeted at 99 at the end. The products have the price from Rs. 199 to Rs. 7,500

PLACE: In the footwear sector especially in retail chain the location of the store is very important. Bata is located in all major cities and metros that too in all prime areas of the cities. In most of the cities, BATA is a landmark. Bata has around 5000 distributors across the country. People look for BATA for their whole family needs.

PROMOTION: Bata does not much rely on advertising. It usually promotes sale in their existing product lines. The following strategies are adopted.

Sales Promotion:

- Display of new Products at cash Counters

Promotion of Brand Equity:

- Gift coupons
- “Discover New” Campaign

POSITIONING

Over the years Bata is positioned a footwear for lower and middle class people for a reliable footwear. People recollect Bata with the White soles with straps.

But now the lower class people started preferring Chinese wear and local shoes, Bata should concentrate on Upper middle class and rich people by offering better products. As Bata is known for reliability, they should concentrate of quality products rather than fashionable wear. By maintaining good relationship with customers, Bata can enjoy the brand equity as it is already an established brand.

POSITIONING OF THE FIRM

Variety- Bata caters to all the segments from lower middle class to middle class people. Now it is concentrating on upper segment also.

Needs- Bata positions itself a family shoe maker.

Access- Bata has vast reach to their customers with their extensive network of showrooms across the country both retail and wholesale as well.

Sustainability of the Positioning- Bata was successful in positioning in the lower and middle segments and it is a test in the upper segments.

Brand Image- Over the decades, Bata is known for lower and middle class people. But currently it has entered into upper segment which creates confusion to the Brand Image. It is has establish its brand image in that segment.

Activities- Bata has a known brand image in the lower and middle segments. Currently it has emerged into upper segment. Having four categories of outlets (A, B, C, D), outsourcing or manufacturing in-house or retailing or wholesale channels do not convey a clear and consistent message yet to the customers about its positioning.

Internal Coordination – Internal coordination is very much required among various business units to convey a clear message to the public.

Sustainability of Competitive Advantage

As Bata is known for lower and middle class for decades, it will be difficult to change the perception of the customers in case of its positioning. Particularly, in upper segment people buy the products to show the brand image or the name. For Bata this first step itself can be difficult.

Bata is an ever green brand. But in 1990s new rivals came to erode the lower and middle class segments at the bottom and the premium segments at the top. Bata had seen its lowest sales in 2004 which compelled to a complete makeover. In March 2008, its Managing Director Marcelo Villagran launched a new advertising campaign to make the store more appealing.

SWOT Matrix

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Brand Image 2. Reasonable quality at low or reasonable price 3. Diversity with ranges in running, training, court, basketball, football and outdoor 4. Footwear for the entire family 5. Financially strong 6. Conveniently accessible outlets in various parts of the country 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No continuity of leadership 2. In 2001, 5% decrease in net sales due to diversification into premier segment (improper targeting and positioning) 3. No proper planning regarding Advertisement and Promotions 4. No variety in Fashionable shoes 5. Lack of Brand Image in the premium segments

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7. Targeting all income segments 8. Provide training for managers and employees 9. Nationwide retail network	
Opportunities 1. E-commerce 2. Acquired, partnership with small players 3. Entering new segments of markets 4. Capturing market where no other potential competitor exists 5. Innovative products 6. New mediums for advertisements	Threats 1. Customer dissatisfaction 2. Price wars with competitors 3. Competitors 4. Political instability 5. Economical threat 6. Changing in consumer preferences

Manufacturing:

Due to its presence across the globe Bata can leverage its international expertise such as in Malaysia for rubber-based shoes, in China for artificial leather shoes to cut down the costs using the economies of scale. It can also stay in International markets to compete with the potential competitors.

Advertising, Sales Promotion and Segmentation Strategy

Bata uses the following strategies for sales promotion and advertising.

Tagline, Print Ads, Tv Ads, Road side Advertising, Celebrity Endorsements with Rani Mukherji. It has specialized shoes in new stores and new retail shops.

PRICE PROMOTION: Price promotion refers to ‘price discounting’. It is done by two ways, namely

DISCOUNTS: Bata offers various types of discounts in all the types of footwear from time to time including seasonal discounts and festival discounts etc.

STOCK CLEARANCE SALE: Bata usually holds ‘Stock Clearance Sale’ boosting the sales figures.

GIFT WITH PURCHASE: For the first time in the footwear industry, Bata introduced Gift Vouchers system to boost up the sales. Apart from it serves the purpose of employee incentives and rewards, business gifting and customer promotions. It can be used in encouraging the customer loyalty with redemption points and in contests as well. The gift vouchers are available in various denominations.

EXCHANGE POLICY: Bata exchanges the products within 7 days if the customer is not satisfied provided the shoes are clean, unused and in their original packing

Distribution:

Bata distribution system is classified into Wholesale channel and retail Channel.

Wholesale Channel is again classified into the following ways:

1. Dealers
2. Wholesalers
3. Industrial and Institutional buyers and
4. Departmental Stores

Dealers

With company owned stores it can be better controlled and operated with offering training programs to the employees to have better quality. With the training they can also open more franchises to get more profits. But to build a good brand image these types of stores is a hindrance.

Wholesalers

These are show traders who buy merchandise to resell to dealers located in rural areas and cities or towns. They keep inventory for replacement and sell on credit or cash basis. Their focus is on volume products and some of them sell to institutions also.

Industrial / Institutional

- Large industries and private and public institutions who want to buy footwear for their employees can approach the wholesale division directly for their requirements to hospitals, military forces, factory workers and airlines for example..

Department Store

These are big multilevel modern and full service stores in metro cities. These consist of medium to high priced shoes for men, women and children with local and international brands in a fully air-conditioned environment.

Retail Store profile classification

Retail strategy is to set up 60 large format stores, closing the non profit stores and increasing the institutional or industrial sales. It has recently opened 32 retail stores in a minimum of area of 3,000 sq ft each.

With the emergence of global village, Indian consumers are aspiring for international standards and world class style. Bata has more than 1500 retail outlets in India and aspire further to start 100 new outlets every year. The whole retail function is classified into the following groups.

Flagship, City, Family and Bazar stores

Flagship

These are the stores in metro cities at high class locations with fashionable products and International brands. These are air-conditioned and luxurious with cozy atmosphere with comprehensive mobile display units with new arrivals.

City

These stores are located in metros and semi metros at high commercial locations with the products suitable for fashionable middle and high income group consumers. These are fully air conditioned with panel display unit for brand promotion with new arrivals.

Family

These stores are located in major cities with products consists of medium to high priced shoes for the whole family. Some of these stores are air conditioned and these shops deal with local brands and with small manufacturers also. These have mass display and standard panel and stooping rods.

Bazar

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These stores are located in non-commercial location as destination stores. The small existing stores are located in thickly populated and saturated markets. The basic purpose of these stores is for substandard clearance and for creating liquidation by selling to low and medium segments.

Brand value

The brand value of Bata is huge and it is an established brand for over 80 years with an excellent relationship with employees and customers too. It has established small towns such as Batanagar, Bataganj in India and Batawa in Canada. IT believes in serving people but not in profit making. It has created a unique image in consumer mind as a footwear producer. Consumer easily recollects Bata when he thinks of footwear. It has positioned itself as, “one Bata, one world”.

BRANDS OF BATA

BABY BUBBLES----Shoes (as well as clothing and accessories in Latam) for infants from birth to 1-year Bata--Shoes for all occasions in one's life

BATA INDUSTRIALS--Protective footwear for various industries

BOBBLEGUMMERS--Stylish and colorful shoes for active kids

COMFIT---Ergonomic design, soft uppers and cushioned insole support are combined to bring an ultimate comfort.

ECO FIT--Eco-friendly shoes, made from ecological organic and biodegradable materials

MARIE CLAIRE--Stylish and chic shoes for confident women

NORTH STAR--The vision of youth – daring, exploratory casual shoes.

PATAPATA-- ideal for sunny outdoor life

POWER--Power, our sports brand that brings out the spirit of the game

SANDAK--Practical plastic injected sandal for the mass market.

SUNDROP--A women's comfort shoe designed for office wear and casual evenings.

WEINBRENNER--Our shoe offering for outdoors and adventure.

Brand story:

It is highly established brand which enjoyed the monopolistic position till 80's with instantly recognizable brown leather sandals and blue-and-white rubber slippers.

Brand Identity

The brand is mostly identified with middle class customers who expect a price range of Rs. 300 to Rs. 1500 for all the age groups.

Brand Personality

The personality of the brand is for whole family, price sensitive, demanding value for money, meeting utilitarian needs, and shoes for a couple of years through our all seasons and without any complaints.

Bata is one of the world's leading footwear retailers and manufacturers with operations across five continents managed by four regional commercial business units (CBUs). World wide presence is its strength and local companies are self-governing benefitting from the link to the international organization for back-office, systems, product innovations and sourcing. Product development and constant improvement of business processes are the two leadership points to offer customer great value and best possible service.

MARKET SEGMENTATION:

INDIA A (14%, includes high disposable income group)

INDIA B (50%, includes people middle class and middle class group)

INDIA C (36%, lower income class group)

COMPETITION

Leading competitors for Bata are Lakhani Shoes, Liberty Shoes, Action Shoes, Woodland, Paragon and Relaxo in organized sectors.

Strategies Adopted

The strategies adopted tackle competition are

- Reasonable quality at low or reasonable price.
- Footwear for the entire family.
- Footwear for all needs e.g. sports, casual footwear, formal-semi formal.
- Conveniently accessible outlets in all parts of the country.
- Prior to entry of local players and the Chinese imports,

COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE ABOVE THE OTHER BRANDS:

MANUFACTURING

Due to its vast presence across the globe, it can import the best practices from the other parts of the globe to handle the manufacturing requirements for slightly trendier lines and lesser volumes. It is using the expertise from Malaysia for rubber based shoes and from China for artificial leather shoes.

Shoe Making Expertise

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Due to its 110 years of experience in manufacturing and their presence in 20 countries with 27 production facilities across the globe, Bata is the leading footwear retailers all over the globe.

Usually Bata sells half the production from their own retail stores and the balance is manufactured to the specifications of whole sale customers or under contract to other footwear companies.

They even got patents for the first removable heel cartridge system for athletic performance footwear in addition to the other patents they have already got. Most of the manufacturing facilities are ISO 9000 certified and the rest are in the process. Bata has its presence in Italy, Canada, Netherlands, Indonesia,

Indonesia Affordable high-value footwear for mainly tropical climates

The Shoe Innovation Center in Indonesia works with a variety of frameworks including technologies, methods, production processes, designs, materials, trend lifestyle research, economic oriented product development and it all helps Bata to be a leader in footwear for both domestic and international markets.

By investing in multi-talented human resources and the latest technology design equipment, the SIC in Indonesia supplies creative services for the manufacturing and marketing of footwear.

Our team is a unique composition of experienced footwear designers and passionate creative designers with multiple backgrounds who are able to capture our consumers' lifestyle needs.

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China, Pakistan and Africa along with many other countries.

CUSTOMER

Because Bata is an established brand, the customer value proposition is substantial to maintain its brand image and loyalty. Bata fulfils whole family needs and the service standards are strictly monitored. The buying experience should be good so that the customers should be willing to pay a bit of premium to the brand.

INTERNAL PROCESS

Bata is restoring its operations management processes, customer management processes, innovation processes and regulatory and social processes to have low cost and to attain economies of scale.

LEARNING AND GROWTH

Bata is more focussed on training its human resources at all the outlets to provide a better buying experience to the customers. Young managers are empowered to attain its goals and to meet the challenges.

The company has three-pronged strategy; setting up 60 large-format stores every year (minimum area of 3,000 sq ft), closing down the unviable ones and increasing its focus on institutional business.

FOCUS ON PRODUCT DESIGN

Bata is focussing on contemporary look to all its footwear in all its retail stores. It is also introducing new offerings for men, ladies, sports personnel and children. It also initiated regular customer feedback process, customer research and training of staff to meet the competition at the earliest. It also consolidated its all manufacturing process, restructured its wholesale and retail divisions.

The wholesale division is segmented into urban and institutional, safety, branding segments and the retail division into flagship stores, smart stores, super stores and family stores. This helped the brand to give a new trendy look from the century old image.

The company eyes the country's defence system to cater their needs for their shoes in the whole year. The total market size of footwear for defence personnel is huge, 12 million pairs per year.

Bata wants to reposition itself into affordable, market driven, fashion conscious, lifestyle brand from the age old image of production-oriented company. They actually want to produce what their customer wants instead of selling them what they produce. They are focusing on better brand recall by opening bigger stores in malls.

BCG Matrix of BATA:

BCG Matrix describes the company's Portfolio analysis with respect to its Market share and current market growth rate. Due to the competition from local brands of unorganized retail and presence of low cost emerging brands like Paragon, Relaxo, Khadims, Sreeleathers etc. Bata is losing its market growth though it has high relative market share. With incomes growing, Bata needs to understand how consumer aspirations change and find ways to meet the changing needs. So, in the coming years, Bata needs to focus on consumer insights, innovation, renovation as well as improved value chain management for a good performance.

Generic competition to the brand

India's per capita shoe consumption or the number of footwear (shoes, chappals, sandals) worn by an individual has gone up from 1.4 shoes a year in 2004 to 2.2 shoes per year in 2010, according to data from the commerce ministry, "While in absolute percentage terms this might not seem like a lot, in a country of a population of one billion people, the fact that in six years people have gone from consuming 1.4 shoes a year to 2.2 shoes a year is a big change," said Suman Roy Burman, president, Khadims, a Kolkata-based manufacturer and retailer. The average shoe consumption in developed countries is about five per person per year.

Comparison with Other Brands

In order to devise a competitive strategy for BATA, we need to analyze Porter's Five Forces Model. The model analyses the different aspects of attractiveness and competitiveness of the market.

Bargaining power of customers:

High

The potential customers for footwear industries can be broadly classified into two categories-five customers who have a huge bargaining power owing to the presence of low cost brands and local products.

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High end customers who prefer to buy discounted and high sale products from retail outlets or through online shopping like Jabong, Myntra, Yebhi etc.

Bargaining power of suppliers:

Low

Shoes are made of leather, rubber and nylon etc. The materials could be classified as commodities, where the manufacturing process adds the value.

For this reason suppliers have limited bargaining power over buyers.

Threat of new entrants:

Low

As this company has established its name in billion hearts, customers are keen to go for well-known brand; hence the prospects of a new entrant in the market are significantly reduced. □

New entrants like Sreeleather, Relaxo are constantly challenging Bata in low cost segment for last 5-10 years.

Threat of substitute products:

High

As customers are often ready to switch brands and try out different products of the competitors in their search for the best possible deal in terms of price, quality of service etc, the threat of substitute products of Khadims, Liberty, Paragon etc is high.

Intensity of competitive rivalry:

High

Rivalry is more intense as there are lots of equally-sized competitors in India e.g- Liberty, Khadims etc.

Aggressive growth strategy of other brands with low switching cost rivalry is more intense in footwear industries.

5.3 Porter's Five Forces Model

Product Development and Diversification

Market Development

Better Quality at Low Cost

Customer Care Initiatives

Strategies adopted over time by the brand to tackle competition or prime market expansion.

To tackle competition and expand the market share, Bata is adopting strategies over time e.g. aggressive retail expansion, promotion of its brands, contemporary styling, and quality control and strengthening its human resources. As far as growth strategies and competencies of Bata are concerned in Prime market expansion, they can be categorized as:

Product Development and Diversification:

The products of Bata are designed for all functional needs like sports, casual footwear, formal, semi-formal and informal for all the segments kids, ladies and gents. With more than 1500 designs in international standards and with affordable pricing Bata today have many brands like

Hush Puppies, Naturalizer, Marie Claire, Sundrops, Dr.Scholl's, Power, Weinbrenner and many others.

Bata now also diversified into Umbrellas, Belts, Bags and Sunglasses etc.

Diversification of Bata

Bata has diversified into the following

Bata build Towns And Factories (1915)

The Energy Industry (1917)

Agriculture (1917)

Forest Farming (1918)

Newspaper Publishing (1918)

Brick Manufacturing (1918)

Wood Processing (1919)

The Rubber Industry (1923)

The Construction Industry (1924)

Railway And Air Transport (1924)

Book Publishing (1926)

The Film Industry (1927)

Food Processing (1927)

Chemical Production (1928)

Tyre Manufacturing (1930)

Insurance (1930)

Textile Production (1931)

Motor Transport (1930)

Sea Transport (1932)

Coal Mining (1932)

Airplane Manufacturing (1934)

Synthetic Fibre Production (1935),

River Transport (1938)

Market Development:

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To increase its customer value proposition, Bata increased its display area for all the segments and launched the trendy designs like Marie Claire, Hush Puppies, North Star etc. Bata is accessible to everyone across the country with its vast presence through outlets.

Bata gets nearly 85 percent of revenue through retail, 14 percent from non retail (dealers/institutional/industrial sales) and balance 1 per cent through exports. Out of this retail sales, 80 - 90 percent come from tier I and tier II cities. These cities are well connected and served by the dealer networks. Further, Bata plans to expand 400 plus cities and rural markets through wholesale distribution.

Better Quality at Low Cost:

Bata is known for its quality at low cost. Major competitor for Bata is Liberty. At the lower end the competition is majorly dominated by china products and at the high end with the international brands.

Customer Care Initiatives:

Bata has strengthened its customer care division recently, called Customer Help Desk with feedback from the customers. The Help Desk assist customers to locate stores, inform product availability, process online orders and to acknowledge the customers feedback. A program namely Passion to Serve is adopted for the sales personnel to enrich periodic promotions.

Bata has its presence in Facebook also getting more “Likes” on its page.

Culture

The Bata has a culture similar to family like and is very casual. Its monologue is “People are our essence.”

Research and development

Bata has six Shoe Innovation Centres (S. I. C) to conduct research in the application of new technologies, materials and designs for more comfort. They provide service from manufacturing to marketing of the shoes.

Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is the most important in any Bata store. It is achieved in the following ways

In any Bata store in the world, they guarantee customer satisfaction.

- Guaranteed purchase
- Wide collection
- Assured quality
- Personalized attention
- Product detail

Target Customers

Bata is targeting all the segments from top to lower end. But it needs to be more focused to tackle the competition.

Value Proposition for the Customers

The Value propositions of Bata for its customers are

- Reasonable quality at low or reasonable price

- Footwear for the entire family
- Footwear catering to various functional needs e.g. sports, casual footwear, formal-semi formal
- Conveniently accessible outlets in various parts of the country
- High social visibility because of its vast presence across the country

Economy and annual growth

By establishing more manufacturing units Bata contributes to the direct and indirect employment in the country and the economy growth.

Annual growth

Bata has record level of net turnover of Rs. 6.429 Billion signifying a 26% growth.

The Company business witnessed its record level with net turnover of Rs. 6.429 billion signifying a growth of 26% and the gross profit at Rs. 2.672 Billion with 23% growth. The operating profit is increased from Rs. 691.095 million to Rs. 848.205 million at an increase of 23%. The profit after taxation was increased to Rs. 585.512 million from Rs. 477.775 million. The turnover is Rs. 20, 984.1 million in the year 2013.

Bata-The Helping Hand

Under social responsibility, Bata donates many free shoes and cash to many charitable organizations.

Special Technology

Bata introduced new technology footwear for kid brands under the School Shoes umbrella, Bata brings you selections like Champ, Tennis, Scout, Naughty Boy, and Ballerina. These are designed to fight odour round the clock. The Built-in Microban which is anti-microbial agent which controls the growth of odour or bacteria or yeast or fungi that causes the stain. Addition of Microban gives an antibacterial protection in the sole to reduce the unpleasant odour and keeps the feet cleaner and fresher. Cushioned insole also adds to the total comfort to the children to play for long hours in the hot sun.

BATA on RAMP

The total revamp that BATA got as a brand in 2005 is aimed at targeting audiences in every income group. And hence, the brand came up with products targeting the youth, corporate executives, working women, sports enthusiasts and children. Prior to this strategy, BATA was considered to be the “Parle-G” of the footwear industry, mass producing shoes and sandals of the same type and features for all kinds of target audiences. Hence the new strategy was a huge development from its previously rigid and old-fashioned brand image. As part of their new strategy, the new brands that came about were: NorthStar(youth), Marie Claire(women), Bubblegummers(kids), Weinbrenner(Men) etc. However, one fundamental strategy that BATA did not execute was the effective promotion of these brands in terms of their advertising. These new brands did not have separate identities of their own and hence did not succeed in creating images of their own.

Exports

BIL (Bata India Limited) exports around 3 million pairs of shoes and other footwear annually, primarily to Western Europe, Middle-East and Far-East markets. Majority of the export is Canvas shoes under leading private labels to customers in the United Kingdom and France.

Men's leather shoes are sold to established retailers in Europe, Middle-East and Far-East.

BIL's most modern leather shoe Factory is located in Hosur (Tamilnadu) and is geared to make international quality footwear for export. This Factory is comparable to the best anywhere in the world with high degree of

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flexibility and is fully equipped to manufacture Men's, Ladies' and Children's cemented and Moccasin shoes and other footwear.

The company has a licensed capacity of 628 lakh pairs per annum spread across its five manufacturing units at Batanagar (Kolkata), Faridabad (Haryana), Bataganj (Bihar), Peenya (near Bangalore), and Hosur (Tamil Nadu). The company has two tanneries - one at Batanagar and the other at Mokameghat (Bihar). The latter is the second largest in Asia. In total, Bata India employs more than 12000 people.

Bata sells over 60 million pairs of shoes every year. South India is a major market for Bata, from where it earns around 40% of its revenue. The company is the market leader in South, with 16% share of the organized footwear market. Of the overall revenue, it derives nearly 85% through retail networks, 14% from non-retail channels (dealers/institutional/industrial sales) and remaining 1% through exports. Thus, the domestic market is the mainstay as far as revenues are concerned.

BATA – Wrong Target challenges in Indian market

Over the years Bata has changed its appeal from a shop that sells Hawaii slippers and Canvas Shoes to a shop that flaunts brands like Reebok, Nike and Marie Claire that always has a special charm with young adults and students.

But, Bata does very little promotional activities. Although Bata has done a lot to revamp the brand, these efforts are not well communicated. Their promotion is restricted to seasonal offers in the form of “Sale”, but the advertisement part is missing. There are rare ads of Bata seen by the customer both in print and electronic media.

Gone are the days when people considered Bata as a brand that only sold hawai slippers and canvas shoes.

Today, Bata caters to the footwear needs of almost every strata of society.

Bata Macho offers a wide variety of footwear options in the Men’s segment. From Sparx and Power to high end brand like Reebok, Nike and Hush Puppies.

Whereas, Bata Damsel tries to ensure that women who turn to Bata for their footwear needs are completely satisfied. Apart from their own products, Bata sells brands like Marie Claire and Hush Puppie through their stores.

Low quality of shoes – threat of shift in production to other areas or countries where wages levels are low if the quality is maintained at same level

Most companies work on subcontract basis – design, component selection and methods of production are given by the buyers and do not provide their own fashion collections, however companies are able to make prototypes based on ideas provided by the buyer

In the early 1990s, Bata decided to move towards high-end segments of the Indian shoe market. It also launched few brands in these segments with higher prices, but landed in trouble.

The segment is meant for companies like Bata. The size of the segment is too low for a company like Bata. The size of the segment is around 5 – 10% of footwear market in India. It could not produce volumes that Bata used to for the traditional footwear. High volumes are essential for Bata for a healthy bottom line.

Bata started neglecting its core segments, which it was serving for nearly a half century. The company started to focus on the top end products at the cost of the lower end products. As a result the smaller players started taking off the market share from Bata in the lower end, while the established players in the top end market challenged

Bata severely. Ultimately the market share of around 15 percent in mid 1980's, fell to 10 percent in mid 1990's and finally the company was in loss of Rs. 42 crores in 1995.

The Bata had to come back to its lower segments as a core focus on it. But the top end brand like Hushpuppies, which it had started are continued selectively in selected stores only.

Future directions for the brand

Bata is trying to focus on women segment by introducing concept stores. It is also going to launch a brand called Sundrops. It already started large stores in malls and try to increase the online sales. To meet the competition Bata is investing Rs 80 crore on modernizing and increasing the production at their manufacturing units.

The government also cut the excise duty on footwear from 12 percent to 6 percent which is a good news of for the stock market. Bata is focusing more on training their employees, consolidation of manufacturing processes and restructuring the non-retail sales division.

Merchandise Overhaul

Bata decided not to sell any low profile products. They literally threw out its entire low-margin inventory in 2005. It has fixed certain operating margin below which it would not sell any products.

It formed a team of 100 professionals for product design, procurement and merchandising. They roll out new designs North Star, Marie Claire, Bubblegummers, Hush Puppies, Wellinbrenner, ambassador, Mocassino, Power and comfit such as for every 15 days. They will also meet their counterparts in Europe every quarter to improve international designs.

Bata customizes its design to the local market. For example Indian women prefer small-sized heels and demand for closed shoes is gradually increasing.

Bata plans to launch four designs everyday and open 70 to 100 stores of atleast 5,000 sq ft every year to shed its image as cheap footwear.

Bata opens 20 to 30 single brand stores every year either standalone or in malls like Lifestyle and Central. It plans to deal brand licensing with global players to widen its portfolio.

Bata changed its sourcing strategy too. It plans to make all five plants in the country that is a specialist for a particular type of footwear. It also plans to source from China and domestic third parties for cost efficiency by cutting its human force by voluntary retirement schemes.

Scale game

The new mantra for Bata is now quality, contemporary design and customer-centricity. For the competitors it is difficult to meet the scale of operations of Bata and in the same way for Bata it is difficult to establish itself like sports wear or a luxury brand like Adidas, Reebok, Nike, Lee Cooper, Woodland and Puma. Infact these companies do not consider Bata as a competitor to them as it is mainly into utility or value-for-money market because of which it is making volumes.

Not stopping with that, Bata continues to open new stores every year with an average size of 3,000 sq ft and renovates the existing stores. On an average, Bata opens over 60 new stores in a year. The focus is on growing its retail business. The new stores are designed by a team of specialists and architects from Italy to be best in their class. The layout of these stores are designed to suit the convenience display of the products with modern furniture and well-lit ambience supported by attractive POP enabling the customers to make better choice in convenience.

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The store staff is also given training for good customer response and customer relations. It employs more than 6,800 people to serve 120,000 customers daily. It has 5 manufacturing facilities across the country and sells over 45 million pairs of footwear every year. The manufacturing set ups are fully equipped with tannery enabling them to cater wide range of customer segments across the country. They focus better quality products with the help of better technology for more trendy looks and to meet ever-changing market requirements.

The product development department focuses on improving products with latest softwares and IT systems. The new products are lightweight rippled flexible soles, soft leather uppers with full padding which are best sellers in their category. The school shoes are also upgraded from a solid PVC sole to air blown lightweight sole with good cushioning for better support and comfort for children. The company always focuses on quality, which made them granted approval by DGMS after meeting their strict Specifications. The Batanagar unit is equipped with Quality Control cum Research and Development Laboratory, which is accredited, by Ministry of Science & Technology, Govt. of India, Bureau of Indian Standard, FDDI and Directorate General of Mines Safety.

Bata Company has a specialized division within the company. They focus on industrial and institutional business. They have highly trained professionals and large distribution network to their credit.

It is worthy to look at the awards the company got with their team and expertise.

Achievements

- Bata India was awarded the Most Admired Large Format Multi-Brand Footwear Retailer of the Year award.
- Customer Loyalty award by Shoes & Accessories and the loyalty award for a wide product range and excellent customer service.
- Brand Equity, acknowledged Bata to be amongst the 50 Most Trusted Brands in a 2010 study.
- In its history the Bata has sold more than 14 billion pairs of shoes and was awarded the Guinness World Record as the "Largest Shoe Retailer and Manufacturer".
- Brand Of The Year Award
- Bata have won the brand of the year award for 2009 and 2010 because it has been serving to the needs and demands of a wide array of customer.

Bata won the award in following categories:

- Power
- Marie Claire
- Bubble gummers

1. Awarded Amity Corporate Excellence Award – 2009 in a ceremony held in Amity Business School, NOIDA on February 27th 2009. Bata received the award for the third time.

2. Business Week lists Bata India in list of “The world’s 25 Unsung Innovative Companies” in its May 2009 issue. The report was compiled by Boston Consulting Group, Business Week’s partner in Annual Most Innovative Companies Special.

3. Awarded Outstanding Sales performance for Year 2008 for Hush Puppies by Wolverine Group-Announced in May 2009 in Michigan

4. Brand Equity recognized Bata in the TOP 50 Most Trusted Brands in June 2009. Bata is the only lifestyle retailer in the top 50 brands.

5. Bata India awarded the prestigious Images award of the year for the Most Admired Retailer of the Year – Fashion & Lifestyle in Mumbai on September 16, 2009. Other nominees in the category were Levis, Benetton, Wills Lifestyle, Bata, Louis Phillipe and Titan

6. Bata India awarded the Most Admired Footwear Brand by Images Fashion Forum in 2009, the ceremony was held in Mumbai on January 28, 2009

7. Bata India received the Amity HR Excellence Award for Corporate Ethics on 28th August 2009 in a ceremony held at Amity Business School, NOIDA.

8. Bata India is selected as a POWERBRAND in the POWERBRANDS 2010. The selection is done after an extensive pan India research conducted by Indian Council for Marketing Research to select The Most Powerful Brands in India in the year 2009.

Future Directions for Brand

Company should focus more on Product and Market Development and Market penetration Strategies.

More attention should be given to the middle and upper middle class of the society, because increasing number of people belonging to these segments and also because of their rising incomes.

Renewed brand image will help Bata to attract upper middle end of the market and will raise the higher income.

As footwear industry is highly fashionable industry; Bata must concentrate on bringing new designs and styles.

The service standards should be strictly monitored and hence an experience fit will be provided to the customers and these customers for this will be willing to pay a bit of premium because of Bata's brand and hence the competition undercutting Bata on price would no longer be that big a threat.

It will need to focus on marketing itself as an outlet meeting all basic needs of the families in its target market segment

Should provide consistent quality service to its customers so that customers can associate the same experience with whichever outlet they visit of Bata.

Internet is a broad medium so they should also improve e-business.

The company should focus on Product Development, Market Development and Market penetration strategies.

It should concentrate more on the middle class and upper middle class people as their number and income are growing.

The brand image should be renewed to gain a premium in the upper middle market.

Bata should launch new design and styles to gain more financial benefits.

The service standards should be enhanced so that the customers should feel the difference with the other brands.

It can also meet the other needs of the customers like entering into accessories division.

The service at all the Bata stores should be consistent so that the customers should feel the same whichever store they visit to.

The debt equity ratio is 3.51, which means almost 75% are debts. This can be reduced to avoid financial charges.

The Selling and Administration expenses also can be reduced to increase the net income.

E-business can be encouraged to cater a large base of customers.

Conclusion:

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The company has already started reworking for recapturing its original market share and its previous customers who have turned towards other brands. But it is a long way to change the perception of the customers who recollects a ration shop or sandals when they hear the name Bata. Bata has to shed the image of its utility products to create a brand image for middle and upper middle class people. But with its team and the leader it believes “NOHING IS IMPOSSIBLE”.

References:

Business Line, December 22, 2006

The Economic Times, May 10, 2006

The Economic Times, May 30, 2011

The Economic Times, May 11, 2011

The Hindu Business Line, May 11, 2011

The Economic Times, May 10, 2011

The Hindu Business Line • Apr 29, 2011

www.bataindustrials.in Auto-hide: on

<http://www.hindustanstudies.com/files/marketmanage.pdf>

http://www.wikinvest.com/stock/Bata_India_%28NSE:BATAINDIA%29

http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2010-02-24/news/28480241_1_egaro-footwear-km-khadim

<http://www.bata.com/us/news/news/news.php?id=634>

<http://www.bata.in/webbata/faces/jsp/static.jsp?articleid=1897&orgId=0&lang=en>

<http://www.bata.in/webbata/faces/jsp/static.jsp?articleid=1966&orgId=0&lang=en>

<http://www.bata.in/webbata/faces/jsp/static.jsp?articleid=1954>